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INTRODUCING THE LINGUISTIC-CULTURAL COMPONENT IN THE SCIENCE LESSON

Abstract. This paper discusses the ways of introducing the linguistic-cultural component in science lessons, particularly for students from diverse cultural backgrounds who speak different languages. It also highlights the opportunity to develop students' language skills and subject matter knowledge through the use of Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) approach. The paper also provides an example of how to incorporate the linguistic-cultural component into a science lesson using beans. Incorporating linguistic and cultural activities in lessons can improve language skills and enhance the overall learning experience.

Keywords: linguistic-cultural component, Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) approach, science teacher education, science lesson planning

Introduction

Introducing the linguistic-cultural component in the science lesson can be a challenge, especially when dealing with students from different cultural backgrounds who speak different languages. However, this challenge can also be seen as an opportunity to develop students' language skills and subject matter knowledge simultaneously, through the use of Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) approach (Marsh, 2002; Coyle et al., 2010).

In Georgia, linguistic and cultural diversity is a sensitive issue, and it is vital to provide education that is sensitive to this diversity. The Erasmus+ ESTA project, which started in 2020, aims to promote more responsible science education through the inclusion of cultural diversity and linguistic heterogeneity issues in science teacher education. The project seeks to develop university curricula and courses for educating future teachers for diversity-sensitive science teaching, by following the model of CLIL and Action Research, providing Continuous Professional Development to in-service science teachers about diversity-sensitive science teaching, and promoting virtual mobility and the use of open educational resources.

Integration of linguistic-cultural components in the science lesson

When teaching science, the linguistic-cultural component can be brought into the lesson through various activities (Coyle et al., 2010). Lesson planning is an essential part of any educational program. Based on the scaffolding principle, it involves several stages that lead to successful learning outcomes. These stages include need analysis, determination of students' knowledge level, determination of the learning objective, lesson planning, providing interesting and necessary information to students, building a "scaffold" based on the needs of students, and effective combination of language and subject teaching (Brunfaut&Revesz, 2019). Activities that can be used for CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) in a science lesson are:

Inquiry-Based Learning: Students can be given a science experiment to perform, where they have to predict, observe, and record data. The teacher can provide the students with a set of guiding questions to help them hypothesize and draw conclusions. This activity will help students develop scientific thinking skills, while also learning the language of science (Westbrook, 2019).

Vocabulary Building: Students can be provided with a list of key vocabulary words related to a particular science topic, such as the human body or photosynthesis. They can then work in pairs or small groups to create flashcards or a glossary with definitions, translations, and visual aids to help them remember the words.

Research Projects: Students can be given a research project on a particular scientific topic, such as climate change or renewable energy. They can work in pairs or small groups to conduct research and create a presentation or report on their findings. This activity will help students develop their research and presentation skills, as well as their language proficiency (Allen, 2010).

Concept Mapping: Students can be asked to create a concept map to show their understanding of a particular scientific concept, such as the water cycle or the rock cycle. They can work in pairs or small groups to brainstorm and organize their ideas, using appropriate scientific language and terminology (Novak&Cañas, 2008).

Role-Playing: Students can be asked to role-play different scientific scenarios, such as a doctor-patient consultation or a scientific debate. This activity will help students develop their language proficiency, as well as their critical thinking and problem-solving skills (Hafner, 2014).

Science Journals: Students can be asked to keep a science journal, where they can record their observations, questions, and reflections on different scientific topics. This activity will help students develop their writing skills, as well as their ability to think critically and reflectively (Keating & Boud, 2018).

To demonstrate how the linguistic-cultural component can be incorporated into a science lesson, in this paper we have included the practical application of vocabulary building, research project, and concept mapping on the example of beans activity. The brochure, Lilu's House, which was created for primary level as part of the Science on Stage project, and was translated

into Georgian in the framework of project ESTA in 2022. One of the activities given in the chapter Kitchen Curiosities is sorting beans, and a teacher can use this as a basis for teaching descriptive language (measuring and weighing).

The activities are designed for the classes with linguistic and cultural diversity to strengthen the official language. The first activity for this lesson is Sorting Beans. For this activity, the teacher prepares up to 30 cards with 5 words from the target language related to this activity. The students are then divided into groups, and each group chooses 5 cards. The task of each group is to create a sentence which is as long as possible using the words on the cards. The sentences can be later presented to the whole class. A teacher can also prepare the list of a verb chain (measure, weigh, describe, sort, put, observe), name chain (beans, ruler, scale, task sheet, color), and chain of ideas (measuring, weighing, sorting, describing, differentiating) (Choi & Kim, 2017). Similarly, the lists can be used to make sentences.

There are several other linguistic and cultural activities that can be used for older students while conducting the bean activity. The teacher can provide students with topics and questions to discuss in groups and make presentations later, such as identifying occupations associated with growing beans, creating proverbs or idioms about beans, exploring the science behind how long it takes for beans to germinate and what conditions favor bean sprouting, connecting to math by determining how many beans should be planted to produce an average of one kilo of beans, creating art by drawing a bean before and after germination, discussing how we can help farmers grow beans, exploring the different varieties of beans popular in the region where the students live, preparing the recipes of different dishes with beans and identifying categories of words related to beans (verb, noun, adjectives, etc.) (Coyle et al., 2010).

Through these activities, students can benefit in several ways, such as improving their content knowledge of bean grain characterization, enhancing their language knowledge through the use of comparative degree of adjectives and verbs necessary for measurement, and developing their communication skills and ability to work in groups.

The science teachers should:

- Incorporate linguistic and cultural components in the science lessons: As discussed in the article, incorporating linguistic and cultural components in science lessons can improve language skills and enhance the overall learning experience. Therefore, science teachers should strive to include activities that promote language acquisition and cultural awareness.

- Use the Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) approach: The CLIL approach is a great way to develop students' language skills and subject matter knowledge simultaneously. Therefore, science teachers should consider using this approach in their lessons.

- Engage in continuous professional development: As the field of education evolves, it is important for science teachers to stay up-to-date with the latest research and teaching strategies.

- Conduct need analysis: Before planning any science lesson, science teachers should conduct a need analysis to determine their students' knowledge level, learning objectives, and needs. This will help science teachers create effective lesson plans that cater to their students' needs.
- Use a scaffold-based approach: Science teachers should use a scaffold-based approach when planning their lessons. This involves building on their students' existing knowledge and providing support to help them reach their learning objectives.
- Incorporate a variety of activities: To cater to the diverse learning styles and cultural backgrounds of their students, science teachers should incorporate a variety of activities in their lessons.
- Be culturally sensitive: Finally, science teachers should be culturally sensitive and aware of the linguistic and cultural diversity of their students. This can involve using culturally relevant examples and activities, being aware of their students' cultural practices and beliefs, and creating a classroom environment that is inclusive and respectful of all students.

Conclusion

In conclusion, incorporating linguistic and cultural activities in lessons not only helps to improve language skills but also enhances the overall learning experience. By providing multiple opportunities for students to use the language in various contexts and using a variety of language models teachers can create a rich learning environment that supports the needs of all learners. Through the use of CLIL approach, teacher training, and effective lesson planning, it is possible to develop students' language skills and subject matter knowledge simultaneously, and provide a more inclusive and culturally sensitive education.

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